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Analysis of Corpers Perception and Attitude towards Community Development Service of the Nigeria NYSC in Abia State

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Research Article

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ABSTRACT

The need for corp members' absolute commitment to Community Development Service (CDS) of the National Youth Service Corp (NYSC) is of immense importance. This study assessed corp members' perception and attitude towards community development service of the Nigeria NYSC in Abia State, Nigeria. Structured and unstructured instruments were administered to 117 randomly selected corp members in the state. Data collected were analyzed using percentage, frequency and mean. Findings of the study revealed that more (49.52%) of the respondents were of western origin, female respondents were of majority (54.70%) and 41.88% of the respondents had a university degree and 35.89% had polytechnics awards. Corp members perceived that CDS is not effective due to the fact that there is no fund allocated to it by the NYSC scheme (mean score 3.22) and that they see it as a waste of time and energy (mean score 3.16). Constraints to the smooth operation of the community development service were inadequate sensitization on CDS operation/functions (mean 3.02), problem of CDS leadership (mean 3.09), lack of CDS operational funds (mean 3.22), fear of area boys attack/kidnapping (mean 2.87). The findings revealed that corp members were not effective because they disliked their CDS group (mean 2.90).

Keywords: Corpers, Perception, Attitude, Community Development Service.

1.1. INTRODUCTION

Nigeria being one of the most populous country in Africa is characterized by multiple languages/multi-socio cultural beliefs and traditional norms with active and energetic young people of the age of 30 years and below making up to 80% of the population and constitute about 76% of the labor force (Onemolease 1992, Adesope 2007) hence the need to improve and intensify the operation of the scheme 'the national youth service corps' which focuses mainly on inculcating into the Nigerian youth the spirit of selfless service to the community as well as emphasizes the spirit of oneness and brotherhood to all Nigerians irrespective of ethnicity, cultural, economic and social background (NYSC, 1992) and more so to promote national unity, integration and development of common ties among the Nigerian youths (NYSC, 2011).

According to Adesope (1993), corpers are young professionals from divers' field who are called upon to serve their father land after graduating from higher institution of learning. These corpers are to render selfless service to the community where they are serving and initiate project that will aid to skyrocketing the nation's economy as well as equip themselves with the concept of professional working ethics/experience for a period of one year.

The NYSC honors every corps members who participated actively and is successful at the end of the service year with a certificate in addition to the national service certificate (Discharge) given to every corps members at the end of the service year. It is worthy of note to highlight that state or national award either in kind or in cash is given to distinguished corps members whose impact and contributions were significantly felt during the service period. A corps member can attract this honor based on the relevance of the project he/she was able to initiate and successfully implement. It is in this light that the national youth service corps scheme of Nigeria states that in addition to the primary assignment, corps members are expected to embark on at least one community development project (CDP) in their neighborhood individually or in groups, after due consultation with the host community [NYSC, 2011].

Without mincing words, it is paramount to accentuate that the significance of the community development service of the Nigeria National Youth Service Scheme in harnessing the nation's economy/abundant resources especially in rural areas of the country cannot be over emphasized. Thus, preliminary interviews with some corps members revealed that among all the program of the NYSC scheme, the Community Development Service (CDS) and the camping experience are (were) the most exciting , interesting and challenging aspect of the program. This informs that there is need for the stakeholders of the scheme to critically and analytically examine and also enhance the quality of programs at Camp and CDS level. The result of this interview, fall in consonance with the findings of

Agumagu et al, (2006) which states that the corps members upheld that the CDS program was an ideal program for corps members and should be made more functional.

The national youth service corps scheme is indeed a channel for national unity and economic development especially with the provision and availability of adequate facilities that will aid functionality and engender competitiveness among prospective corps members and not just persuasive and mandatory concept as it is today. According to the global Conference on National Youth Service Report (1998), the benefit that a national youth service scheme could bring to a nation cannot be over emphasized hence for programs such as this; however, outcomes/result depends on design, what the youth brings to the service, attitude of the youth to service, perception and experience of the youth in service. The report further revealed that the evaluations of National Youth Service (NYS) in other countries where the scheme has been deemed to be successful showed that the value of service rendered by participant is equal to or greater than the cost of the program; and that participant benefit from work experience and where provided with opportunities for career exploration, increased self esteemed and increased awareness of the needs of others. Among all, it is expected that the benefits that should be recorded at the end of every service year should significantly outweigh the input/resource used in running the program for that period.

In view of the above, it can be stated that establishing the relevance and benefits of a national youth service scheme for Nigeria, exclusion of internationally accepted definitions of terms related to national youth service and features common to successful program in addition to possible benefit of a well run program should not be undermined or relegated. Based on the varying opinion of the national youth service corps scheme of Nigeria in terms of input/effort of federal and state government and the outcome/attitude portrayed by corps members, a prompt question such as this may likely erupt; is the NYSC program actually beneficial? To a very large extent, it can be agreed that the benefits acclaimed for the scheme both in the nation and to individual participant have been based largely on assumption rather than on qualitative/empirical base line (Nigeria village square, 2006). It further states that participants are generally not known to speak highly of the scheme and that many consider it a waste of time which contradicts the findings of Agumagu et al, (2006) which revealed that participant did not agree that the CDS/NYSC was a waste of time and energy.

At this juncture, it is worthy of note to pinpoint that the attitude of corps members towards the Community Development service (CDS) of the National (Nigeria) Youth Service Corps calls for chronological and critical investigation hence observation reveals that the attendance level of corps members to CDS Meetings was poor. Also, personal interviews with some corps members accentuated that they were not committed to CDS meetings/programs due to lack of interest in their CDS group, lack of motivation from leadership, as well as operational fund to execute community development project. It was based on this inconclusive and challenging pre-expository insight by serving corps members that engendered the study. Thus, the study examined corps members perception and attitude towards community development service of the NYSC in Abia state, Nigeria, and specifically addressed the following research questions;

- i. How do corps members perceive the CDS of the NYSC?
- ii. What kind of attitude do corps members portray towards the CDS program?
- iii. Which factor significantly inhibits the effective execution of the CDS project by Corps members?
- iv. Should the NYSC Scheme be prompted or scrapped?

1.2 METHODOLOGY

The study population was 2350 Batch A corps members who served in Abia State Nigeria in the 2013/2014 service year. Corps members were visited during their community development service at the local government council. Simple random sampling technique was employed to select a sample size of 117 corps members who did their orientation/camping in the state and this constituted the sample for the study.

The instrument used for data collection was a 4-sectioned structured and unstructured questionnaire. Section A, B, C and D elicited information on Socio-economic Characteristics, Perception, and Attitude, and Constraints to CDS operation by corps members respectively. Respondents' responses to items in section B, C & D were measured using a 20, 15 and 13- item statement on a 4-point rating scale of Strongly Agreed, Agreed, Disagreed and Strongly Disagreed.

Data generated from the study was analyzed by the use of descriptive statistics such as frequency, percentage and mean scores. A mid-point of 2.50 was established for the purpose of result interpretation. The decision rule was that any mean score that is less than 2.50 implies disagreement with the statement while the reverse was the case for mean scores greater than 2.50.

1.3 RESULTS

The result of socio-economic characteristic in table 1 shows the percentage of corpers from southern states to be 9.40%, western states 49.52%, northern states 24.72% while eastern state was 16.23%. Among the respondents used for the study, 64.95 were science students during their secondary education while 35.04 were arts students. The study revealed that 41.88% of the corpers were university graduates, 35.89% were graduates of polytechnics, 18.80% was of monotekniques and 3.41% were graduates of university of education (formally known as COE). Female respondents were of majority (54.70%) as only 45.29% were males. 64.95% of the corpers never embarked on any development project prior to the time of the study while 35.04% had embarked on one developmental project or the other. 61.53% of the corpers were married while 38.46% were single as at the point of the research.

Table 1: Socio-economic Characteristics of respondents

S/N	Variables	Percentage [%]	Frequency [f]
1.	State of Origin:		
	Southern State	9.40	11
	Western State	49.52	58
	Northern State	24.72	29
	Eastern State	16.23	19
2.	Secondary Educational Background:		
	Sciences	64.95	76
	Arts	35.04	41
3.	Type of Higher Institution Attended:		
	University	41.88	49
	COE	3.41	4
	Polytechnics	35.89	42
	Monotekniques	18.80	22
4.	Sex of Respondent:		
	Male	45.29	53
	Female	54.70	64
5.	Have you embarked on any development project before?		
	Yes	35.04	41
	No	64.95	76
6.	Marital status:		
	Single	61.53	72
	Married	38.46	45
7.	Family residential area:		
	Urban	45.29	53
	Rural	57.70	64
8.	Occupation of Father:		
	Self Employed	41.02	48
	Public Servant	27.35	32
	Private Organization	31.62	37
9.	Community development service joined:		
	ICPC	17.94	21
	Sanitation	37.60	44
	EFCC	24.78	29
	Publicity	19.65	23

The result on perception of corpers towards community development service in table two shows that item 16 has the highest mean score (3.42), followed by item 15 (3.22), item 13 (3.13), item 10 (3.12), item 19 (3.01) while item 1 had (2.82). The study revealed that corpers strongly uphold that every community development project initiated by each corps members or community development service group, should be sponsored by the state government, via the local government council hence the (mean score 3.42). This was complimented by item 15 which had the second highest mean score of 3.22. The respondents strongly believed that community development service (CDS) is not efficient because there were no adequate and readily available fund allocated to it by the scheme. Item 4 and 14 had the same mean score and ranked the least in the table. The items states that corpers are not committed to CDS because they are not in their community (1.71) and community development project embarked by corpers does not benefit the community in any way (mean score: 1.71), every other item in table two had a mean score less than 2.5 and greater than 1.5, thus indicating a strong disagreement with the statement.

Table 2: Perceptual of Corpers towards Community Development Service

S/N	Variable	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Remark
1.	Community development services should be carried out by non government Agencies	45(38.4)	35(29.9)	15(12.8)	22(18.8)	2.82	Agreed
2.	I perceive that CDS is usually carried out by government agencies	32(27.3)	28(23.9)	23(19.6)	34(29.1)	2.41	Disagreed
3.	I believe that CDS is for corp members who studied development courses	18(15.3)	9(7.6)	61(52.1)	29(24.7)	2.10	Disagreed
4.	I am not committed to CDS because am not in my community	11(9.4)	8(6.8)	41(35.0)	57(46.7)	1.71	Disagreed
5.	Community development service is always tedious	16(13.6)	14(11.9)	58(49.5)	29(24.7)	2.12	Disagreed
6.	I don't like CDS because the community don't appreciate my effort	21(17.9)	18(15.3)	49(41.8)	29(24.7)	2.23	Disagreed
7.	I believe that CDS is not important for me because am not a community developer	6(5.1)	13(11.1)	63(53.8)	35(29.9)	1.93	Disagreed
8.	CDS is dangerous and risky because of area boy's attack	8(6.8)	9(7.6)	68(58.1)	32(27.3)	1.94	Disagreed
9.	I believe CDS should be carried out by community members	24(20.0)	26(22.2)	42(35.8)	25(21.3)	2.42	Disagreed
10.	I feel that every CDS member should be given an incentive in order to propel Their interest towards executive a given task	41(35.0)	53(45.2)	17(14.5)	6(5.1)	3.12	Agreed
11.	I believe that CDS is for change agents in the state and not corpers	26(22.2)	20(17.0)	38(32.4)	33(28.2)	2.33	Disagreed
12.	I feel that CDS is not suppose to be compulsory for all corpers	18(15.3)	28(23.9)	26(22.2)	45(38.4)	2.14	Disagreed
13.	Corpers should be allowed to join any CDS at will	42(35.8)	56(47.8)	14(11.9)	5(4.2)	3.13	Agreed
14.	Community development project embarked on by corpers does not help the Community in any way	9(7.6)	12(10.2)	36(30.7)	60(51.2)	1.72	Disagreed
15.	CDS is not efficient because there is no fund allocated to it by NYSC Scheme	61(52.1)	34(29.0)	7(5.7)	15(12.8)	3.22	Agreed
16.	I feel that every state government via the local government areas should Sponsor each community development project initiated by any corper or CDS group	58(49.5)	53(45.2)	1(0.8)	5(4.2)	3.42	Agreed
17.	I feel that the CDS coordinators should strictly outline projects to be embarked upon by the group annually	31(26.4)	26(22.2)	28(23.9)	32(27.3)	2.43	Disagreed
18.	I think the reason CDS is not effective is because CDS coordinators are not committed to the task	12(10.2)	16(13.6)	47(40.1)	42(35.8)	1.92	Disagreed
19.	I don't think CDS can affect my life positively and that's why am not Interested	47(40.1)	38(32.4)	24(20.5)	8(6.8)	3.01	Agreed
20.	I think CDS can improve my development initiatives, skill and competence	9(7.6)	16(13.6)	55(47.0)	37(31.6)	1.9	Disagreed

*** Mean Score \geq 2.50 implies Significance

Table 3 presents result on analysis of corpers attitude towards CDS. The respondents strongly agreed with item 1 and 2 in spite of the fact that the respondents were always involved in CDS (mean score: 3.30) yet they saw it as a waste of time (mean score: 3.16). An average number of the respondents [mean score: 2.52] indicated that they always pay their dues and contributions for CDS projects. Findings unveiled that some corpers were not effective in their CDS groups due to the fact that they hated it (mean score 2.90). Corpers did not agree that their CDS group do not hold weekly meetings (mean score 1.31) and that they were not part of any CDS group (mean score 1.01).

Table 3: Analysis of Corpers Attitude towards Community development Service

S/N	Variable	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Remark
1.	I see CDS to be a waste of time for corpers	52(44.2)	43(36.7)	8(6.4)	13(12.2)	3.16	Agreed
2.	I am always involved in CDS	61(52.1)	38(32.4)	12(10.4)	6(4.9)	3.30	Agreed
3.	I support my CDS group in all they do	15(12.8)	12(10.2)	44(37.6)	46(39.3)	1.96	Disagreed
4.	I attend my CDS meetings only during PV signing	11(9.4)	21(17.9)	58(49.5)	27(23.0)	2.13	Disagreed
5.	I have a record of all the projects my CDS has carried out	9(7.6)	23(19.6)	65(55.5)	20(17.0)	2.17	Disagreed
6.	I am not effective because I hate my CDS group	36(30.7)	43(36.7)	29(24.7)	9(7.6)	2.90	Agreed
7.	I am not fully involved in CDS because there is no pay for it	14(11.9)	16(13.6)	51(43.5)	36(30.7)	2.06	Disagreed
8.	I come to CDS meetings at least once a month	11(9.4)	13(11.1)	43(36.7)	50(42.7)	1.86	Disagreed
9.	My CDS do not hold weekly meetings	2(1.7)	1(0.8)	29(24.7)	85(72.6)	1.31	Disagreed
10.	I am not part of any CDS group	0(0)	0(0)	1(0.8)	117(1.0)	1.01	Disagreed
11.	My attitude to CDS is fair	38(32.4)	43(36.7)	21(17.9)	17(14.5)	2.92	Agreed
12.	I will like to improve on my attendance to CDS	15(12.8)	29(24.7)	52(44.4)	21(17.9)	2.32	Disagreed
13.	My CDS group do not have any specified time for meeting	3(2.5)	6(5.1)	31(26.4)	77(65.8)	1.17	Disagreed
14.	I am not committed to CDS here because am not in my state of origin	8(6.8)	11(9.4)	52(44.4)	46(39.3)	1.83	Disagreed
15.	I always pay my dues/contributions for CDS project	41(35.0)	39(33.3)	16(13.6)	21(17.9)	2.52	Agreed

*** Mean Score \geq 2.50 implies Significance

Table 4 displays the result of constraints to CDS operation. The findings reflected that variety/multiple factors inhibit corpers involvement in CDS operation/activities. Corpers strongly agreed that lack of good ideas (mean score: 2.62), inadequate sensitization on CDS operations (mean score 3.02), lack of operational facilities (mean score 2.80), lack of operational fund for community development project (CDP) (mean score 3.22), lack of interest by corpers (mean score 2.79), fear of area boys attack/ kidnapping (mean score 2.87) were the major constraints to corpers CDP operation.

Table 4: Analysis of Constraints to CDS Operation

S/N	Variable	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Remark
1.	Lack of good ideas is a major constraints to CDS operation	31(26.4)	42(35.8)	16(13.6)	28(23.9)	2.62	Agreed
2.	Inadequate sensitization on CDS operations/Functions	48(41.0)	36(30.7)	21(17.9)	12(10.2)	3.02	Agreed
3.	Lack of operational facilities	50(42.7)	26(22.2)	18(15.3)	23(19.6)	2.80	Agreed
4.	Money consciousness among the group leaders	26(22.2)	18(15.3)	45(39.2)	28(23.9)	2.35	Disagreed
5.	Problem of leadership/mode of leadership structure/setup	46(39.3)	42(35.8)	23(19.6)	6(5.1)	3.09	Agreed
6.	Lack of motivation/incentive by the CDS coordinators	58(49.5)	34(29.0)	9(7.6)	11(9.4)	3.10	Agreed
7.	Lack of CDS operational fund/capital	52(44.5)	41(35.0)	22(18.8)	2(1.7)	3.22	Agreed
8.	Lack of interest by corp members	38(32.4)	46(39.3)	16(13.6)	5(4.2)	2.79	Agreed

9.	Too many lines of action / project to be executed	28(23.9)	32(23.3)	48(41.1)	9(7.6)	2.67	Agreed
10.	Fear of area boys attack/kidnapping	33(28.2)	46(39.3)	28(23.8)	10(8.5)	2.87	Agreed
11.	Inadequate monitoring team by NYSC officers	18(15.3)	25(21.3)	19(16.2)	55(47.0)	2.05	Disagreed
12.	Lack of understanding among group members	11(9.4)	40(34.1)	54(46.1)	12(10.2)	2.42	Disagreed
13.	Poor management of finance	21(17.9)	31(26.4)	44(37.6)	21(17.9)	2.44	Disagreed

*** Mean Score \geq 2.50 implies Significance

Table 5 presents result on general appraisal of corps members towards the community development service of the NYSC. 47% of the corpers confirmed that poor response to dues/attendance [Interest] to CDS meetings were the most significant challenge in their CD group. 73% of corpers were of the opinion that the NYSC scheme should be promoted and supported while 26% suggested it should be scrapped. 52.1% rated the research as relevant, 30.7% as interesting, 12.8% as educating, while 4.2% rated it as motivating. Majority of the corpers [52%] agreed that assuming they will be the next director general of the NYSC, they would endeavour to improve on posting methods/strategy, while 33% revealed that they would like to improve on the amount and payment of allowance, and 14% confirmed that they would like to improve on the infrastructures and coordination of programs at the orientation camps.

Table 5: General Appraisal of the study

S/N	Variables	Frequency/f	Percentage
1	Which among the following Challenges are significant in your CDS?		
	Poor CDS coordination	32	27.35
	Lack of initiative/impactful projects	22	18.78
	Problems of meeting venue	7	5.98
	Poor response to dues/attendance	56	47.88
2	What do you think of the NYSC Scheme?		
	Promoted/supported	86	73.50
	Scrapped	31	26.49
3	Assuming you are the next director general of NYSC what area would you improve?		
	Posting method/pattern	61	52.1
	Payment of allowance	39	33.3
	Orientation camp	17	14.5
4	How would you rate this research?		
	Relevant	61	52.1
	Interesting	36	30.7
	Educating	15	12.8
	Motivating	5	4.2

1.4 DISCUSSIONS

One of the objectives of the NYSC which is to expose graduates from various higher institutions in the country to areas with different, cultural and socio economic behaviors, was reflected in this study as the majority of the respondents (49.5%) were of western states and 24.7% were of northern states. This implies that greater percentage of the respondents in the study area were of northern and western states of Nigeria hence only 16.2% and 9.4% were of eastern and southern states respectively. Observations revealed that the respondents from neighboring states were mainly female corps members and were either pregnant corps members, nursing mother or married corps members. Corpers with university degree/background were more [41.8%] than others and this may be attributed to the high level of students [university aspirant] interest to seeking admission into university than other higher institutions in the country. The findings are in line with the choice of university aspirant every year, as more students select universities as first choice than polytechnics, monotechnics and colleges of education. Greater percentage of the corpers were female (54.7%) and 64.9% had not embarked upon any developmental project, this goes to unveil the need for

adequate and result oriented sensitization on community development project/programs for corps members prior and during community development service/meetings. The corps members felt that community development projects should be embarked upon by non government agencies [mean score 2.82]. Respondents strongly uphold that joining of any CDS at will by individual corps members will enhance the CDS (mean score 3.12). This implies that corps members are allocated to any CDS irrespective of the corps members' disposition, passion, aptitude, interest and area of specialty/discipline. This is one of the essential reasons for poor performance and attendance to CDS. Corps members agree that they would be more committed to CDS if incentives will be given in order to propel their interest and facilitate their task (mean score 3.12). The respondents also revealed that CDS cannot positively affect their lives hence the reason for lack of interest (mean score 3.01), in spite of the fact that corps members did not agree that CDS is not supposed to be compulsory for all corps members (mean score 2.1), i.e. it should be compulsory, yet revealed that they are not motivated and disagree that CDS can improve their development, initiative, skills and competence [mean score 1.92], this unveils the fact that the present state of corps members involvement in CDS activities is not encouraging. The findings showed that corps members saw CDS as a waste of time [mean score: 3.16] and this was not consistent with the findings of Agumagu et al, [2006] which state that corps members did not agree that CDS was a waste of time and energy. The result of the study exposed a contradiction in corps members involvement (mean score 3.30) and support (mean score: 1.96), this implies that corps members were involved in CDS but did not support their operation hence the mean score 3.30 and 1.96 respectively and this may be attributed to the fact that most of the corps members were forcefully attached to CDS group that was not their choice and this affected their commitment level in the group as was confirmed by item 6 in table 3 (mean score 2.90). Corps members did not agree that they had records of project embarked upon in their group hence the mean score (2.17) and this is probably due to lack of interest. Respondents indicated that their attitude to CDS was fair (mean score: 2.90) and disagreed with the statement that they attended CDS meeting only during Signing of Payment Voucher (PV) (mean score: 2.13), also disagreed that they were not committed to CDS because they were not in their state of origin (mean score: 1.83); this connotes that state of service did not significantly influence their involvement, support, interest and commitment to CDS operations.

Multiple factors inhibit effective CDS operation. These factors ranged from lack of CDS operational fund (mean score: 3.22) which ranked first among the constraint, to lack of good ideas (mean score: 2.62) which ranked the least among the significant constraints to CDS operation. A critical examination of these constraints will help to improve the mode of leadership structure/setup (mean score: 3.01), CDS awareness program (mean score: 3.02), operational facility (mean score 2.81), lack of motivation/incentives (mean score: 3.12), insecurity/kidnapping (mean score: 2.87) etc, respondents strongly uphold that these factors inhibited their CDS operation. It is essential to pinpoint that there may not be effective CDS operation without operational facilities/fund thus most CDS operation seems to be capital intensive for instance sanitation CDS, Mass Literacy CDS, etc. The respondents specifically pointed out that who leads the CDS group was paramount to their performance/achievement hence leadership structure/setup was a significant constraint to their CDS operation. The respondents did not agree that inadequate monitoring by NYSC official was a major constraint to their operation hence the mean score (2.05), nevertheless, there were records of poor CDS coordination (27.35%), lack of impactful project (18.78%) and poor response to dues and attendance (47.88%) as challenges to CDS (table 5).

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The respondents expressed fair perception/disposition towards the CDS of the NYSC yet were not totally committed to their task due to lack of interest and incentives. The issue of fund and funding is paramount to CDS operation. Attendance to CDS meetings was highlighted to be poor and this calls for adequate monitoring by the CDS coordinators. The attitude of corps members towards seeing CDS as a waste of time in the study area is crucial and will invariably limit the actualization of the goals and objective of the scheme. In spite of the fact that corps members were mandated to be part of CDS group, they were not excited and fulfilled in some of their groups as their support, skills and potentials were not adequately harnessed and tapped. It was revealed that majority (52.1%) of the respondents indicated that one of the areas that needed to be improved was posting strategies, followed by payment of allowance (33.3%). This implies that the corps members were not satisfied with the posting methods of the NYSC. In spite of the seemingly conflicting issues on posting approach and the public perception of the scheme, majority of corps members (73.50%) were of the opinion that the scheme should be promoted and supported while a minor fraction of 26.49% suggested it should be scrapped. It is therefore recommended that for effective and efficient CDS operation within the state, corps members should be adequately oriented and allowed to choose a community development service group that is in line with their discipline, passion etc, corps members should be posted to areas where their potentials will be promptly and adequately harnessed. Improvement of corps members allowance, infrastructural development, and packaging of entrepreneurship programs at the orientation camp should be analytically considered by the scheme. Strong awareness campaign on the relevance of community development service project to individual corps members, community and Nigeria at large should be carried out more tactically at the orientation camp and during CDS. Corps members should be encouraged to vehemently initiate and execute personal community development project. It is also suggested that a research be conducted to ascertain if the input/resources invested into the scheme is complimented

by the results/achievements made at the end of every service year, and that the scheme should be made voluntary instead of compulsory to graduates of higher institutions so as to ascertain the readiness and willingness of the youth to take up this one year training hence it is better to have few graduates that will be committed to the task, than have multitude of unwilling youth in the scheme. And Agricultural Extension Society of Nigeria [AESON], should partner with the NYSC to successfully execute rural development project.

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